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Késia Decoté Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow, Grieg Academy, University of Bergen.

a letter for Louise

Key words: music performance; motherhood; improvisation; collaboration

Sorry

We're having a little trouble.

Last year when I was pregnant, my plans for my concerts after the birth of the baby included premiering large works and performing a body of other new pieces. When baby Louise was born, the reality of motherhood showed very different from my expectations. The baby would be delighted to listen to some of my piano practice, but would not take well some pieces. Also, the demands of a young baby would not give me the time to go through longer works. There was then the need to reshuffle my plans of repertoire for these after-baby concerts, working on programmes which would fit into my new reality, and still be artistically relevant. The programme of "a letter for Louise" features pieces which the baby enjoyed listening to, also pieces which have been dedicated to daughters or mothers. Contextualising the musical experience into our new universe, I also improvise over recordings of Louise when she was a newborn. This programme is an artistic reflection on the delights and challenges of this new life, specially about the balance between motherhood and professional life.

This concert programme was developed just before I started my postdoctoral research on audience participation in online concerts. Although not initially related to the research project, this programme has yet inspired preliminary reflections on the acknowledgment and inclusion of someone else's parameters in a concert programme, also about collaboration and the sense of ownership as the artist presenting the work.

References

- NICOLLS, Sarah. 2014. *Moments of Weightlessness*. Music theatre show.
- WHITE, Gareth. 2013. *Audience Participation in Theatre: Aesthetics of the Invitation*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

About Késia

Késia Decoté (Dr Késia Decoté Rodrigues) is a Brazilian pianist specialising in contemporary music and in interdisciplinary practices. Késia has been developing a diverse career performing as a soloist, improviser, and chamber musician, with concerts and premieres in Brazil, Europe and Canada.

Késia's debut solo album 'Para a frente' (released by Nonclassical, London) features piano and toy piano works dedicated to her by emerging UK-based composers. A keen improviser, Késia has also released 'Hour' - an album of improvisations with cellist Bruno Guastalla. Késia's newest CD, 'Isolation', presents a collection of piano miniatures written by British composer Charlotte Botterill reflecting on her experience of the lockdown due to the pandemic crisis in 2020.

Késia is also committed to promoting works by women composers. She has toured the UK with Illuminate Women's Music, and is an ambassador for DONNE UK - Women in Music.

Késia holds a PhD in Arts & Music and MA (Distinction) from Oxford Brookes University, Masters Degree and Undergraduate (Cum laude) in Piano from the federal university of Rio de Janeiro.

She is a Marie Curie postdoctoral fellow at the University of Bergen developing a research project on new forms of participation of women and girls in classical music performances.